

Improving Security in Container Systems

Mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk (*)

This survey is an initial part of the interview you'll be participating in. Its main purpose is to save your time by collecting demographic information about your background and experience with containers. We greatly appreciate your cooperation.

1. Please enter your ID number. You will find it in the interview invitation. *

ID *

2. Which country are you working in? *

Please enter the country *

3. What is your job title? *

Please enter job title *

4. How many years have you been working with SW containers? *

Please enter the number of years *

5. How many projects have you participated in that used containers for deployment? *

Please enter the number of projects *

6. What is your role in container projects? *

7. What are the domains for which you are developing container applications? *

Please add the domains *

8. Please choose the security issues you faced during your work in container\microservices.

Untrusted image source

Image poisoning

High-risk base image

Outdated NPM package

Unused image functions

Application privileged access

- Insufficient host hardening
- Insecure host OS network stack
- Shared host resources
- Docker daemon misconfiguration
- Covert channel exploitation
- Container root privilege escalation
- Namespace exploitation
- Notary server verification bypass
- Outdated seccomp profile
- TF smell
- Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) strip
- Resource authorization flaw
- Misconfigured (CNI) plugins
- Traffic encryption
- Unfiltered Traffic
- Misconfigured HostIPC
- Unverified Packets in the network path
- Container runtime misconfiguration